

Aerial Human Detection and Lightweight Pedestrian Tracking for Edge-Deployed UAV Surveillance

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Abstract—Human detection and tracking in aerial drone imagery is challenging because people often occupy only a few pixels and scenes frequently contain motion blur, occlusions, rapid camera movement, and varying crowd densities. This paper presents The Aerial Guardian, a lightweight UAV surveillance framework for real-time human detection and multi-object tracking. The system combines a fine-tuned YOLOv8s detector with a customized ByteTrack-inspired tracker. To improve the detection of small human targets, an overlapping sliding-window tiling strategy is applied during dataset preparation, producing 11,205 annotated image patches from four VisDrone2019-MOT sequences. Additional aerial-specific augmentations and scale-aware preprocessing are used to improve robustness across different altitudes and environmental conditions. For tracking, a graveyard-based identity recovery mechanism with motion-consistency backtracking is introduced to maintain object identities through short-term occlusions and missed detections without relying on appearance-based re-identification networks. On the VisDrone2019-MOT validation set, the detector achieves an mAP50 of 0.942, precision of 0.96, and recall of 0.93. After ONNX FP16 export, the 22 MB model runs at 6.6 FPS on CPU, making it suitable for deployment on resource-constrained UAV platforms.

Index Terms—YOLOv8, Multi-Object Tracking, Small Object Detection, Aerial Human Detection, UAV Surveillance

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of drone-based surveillance systems has rapidly expanded across applications such as disaster management, crowd analysis, border monitoring, traffic observation, and public safety operations. Compared to fixed surveillance infrastructure, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) provide flexible mobility, dynamic viewpoints, and large-area scene coverage, making them highly suitable for real-time environmental monitoring. Despite these advantages, reliable human detection and tracking from aerial footage remains difficult because individuals often appear at extremely small scales and are frequently affected by occlusion, camera motion, scene density, and motion blur. Recent progress in deep learning has enabled real-time object detection systems with strong performance on conventional benchmarks. Among these approaches, the YOLO family of detectors has gained popularity because of its balance between speed and accuracy. However, models trained on standard ground-view datasets often perform poorly in aerial scenarios where human targets occupy only a limited number of pixels. In addition, many existing multi-object tracking methods depend on appearance-based re-identification networks, which become unreliable when visual features are weak or indistinguishable in high-altitude imagery.

This work introduces The Aerial Guardian, a lightweight UAV surveillance framework designed for efficient human detection and tracking in aerial video streams. The proposed pipeline integrates a fine-tuned YOLOv8s detector with a customized ByteTrack-inspired tracking module optimized for small-object aerial scenes. To improve detection quality, a sliding-window tiling approach is applied during training to enlarge the effective representation of distant human targets and improve robustness in dense environments. The tracking stage further employs an IoU-driven association strategy implemented using pure NumPy operations, reducing computational overhead by avoiding expensive appearance embedding networks.

The framework is trained and evaluated using the VisDrone2019 MOT benchmark, which contains challenging aerial sequences captured under varying viewpoints and altitudes. To support practical edge deployment, the system incorporates lightweight architectural design choices together with ONNX-based inference optimization. The overall pipeline delivers competitive detection accuracy, lightweight tracking stability, and real-time performance suitable for edge-deployed aerial surveillance applications.

II. RELATED WORKS

The increasing use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for surveillance, traffic monitoring, and public safety applications has driven significant interest in aerial multi-object tracking (MOT). Compared with conventional ground-based datasets, UAV videos present additional challenges, including drastic viewpoint variations, camera motion, scale changes, object occlusions, and low-resolution pedestrian appearances. To address these challenges, the VisDrone-MOT2019 Challenge introduced a large-scale benchmark specifically designed for evaluating object tracking methods in drone-captured videos [1].

The VisDrone-MOT2019 benchmark evaluates complete tracking-by-detection systems in which object detection and trajectory association are jointly considered. Participating approaches employed a variety of modern object detectors, including Cascade R-CNN, Faster R-CNN, RetinaNet, CenterNet, and R-FCN, followed by different association strategies for maintaining object identities across frames [1]. Many methods incorporated appearance-based Re-Identification (Re-ID) models to improve identity consistency, while others relied on motion estimation techniques such as optical flow,

KLT feature tracking, Kalman filtering, and recurrent neural networks to model temporal object behavior [1].

Among the submitted methods, DBAI-Tracker achieved the highest average precision (AP) score of 43.94, followed by TrackKITSY with 39.19 AP and Flow-Tracker with 30.87 AP [1]. The leading solutions combined high-quality object detectors with temporal motion information and appearance cues to improve tracking robustness. DBAI-Tracker utilized Cascade R-CNN together with GOG and KCF tracking modules, whereas Flow-Tracker integrated optical-flow-based motion estimation to compensate for camera movement and recover unmatched targets. TrackKITSY demonstrated strong pedestrian tracking capability through motion-pattern analysis specifically designed for small-object tracking in aerial imagery [1].

Analysis of the challenge results revealed that both appearance representation and motion modeling play important roles in UAV-based tracking systems [1]. Re-ID features were found to be beneficial for associating detections under occlusion, while motion-based approaches improved robustness when camera movement or temporary detection failures occurred. Despite these advancements, the challenge organizers concluded that aerial multi-object tracking remained a highly challenging problem, with frequent identity switches and fragmented trajectories still affecting overall performance [1].

To address limitations associated with conventional association strategies, ByteTrack introduced a novel tracking framework that utilizes both high-confidence and low-confidence detections during data association [2]. Traditional MOT methods commonly discard low-confidence detections before matching, which can lead to missed objects and interrupted trajectories. ByteTrack instead performs a two-stage association process in which high-confidence detections are matched first, followed by a secondary association stage that evaluates remaining tracks against lower-confidence detections [2]. This strategy enables the recovery of partially occluded or difficult-to-detect objects while simultaneously suppressing background false positives.

Experimental results reported in ByteTrack demonstrated substantial improvements in identity preservation and tracking accuracy across multiple MOT benchmarks, achieving state-of-the-art performance while maintaining real-time inference speed [2]. The study further showed that effective tracking can be achieved primarily through motion and spatial consistency without heavily relying on computationally expensive appearance-based Re-ID networks [2].

Motivated by the findings of VisDrone-MOT2019 [1] and the association mechanism proposed in ByteTrack [2], the present work develops a customized ByteTrack-inspired tracking framework for aerial pedestrian surveillance. The proposed approach extends conventional motion-based association through graveyard-based identity recovery and motion-consistency backtracking, enabling improved trajectory continuity while maintaining a lightweight inference pipeline free from appearance-based Re-ID models.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework processes aerial UAV video through a five-stage pipeline, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. System pipeline of The Aerial Guardian.

A. Dataset Preparation

This work employs the VisDrone2019-MOT validation dataset to evaluate aerial pedestrian detection and tracking in UAV-based surveillance scenarios. The benchmark contains challenging drone-captured environments with significant variations in object scale, partial occlusion, motion blur, and dense pedestrian regions.

Four UAV video sequences were selected for experimental analysis: `uav0000086_00000_v`, `uav0000117_02622_v`, `uav0000137_00458_v`, and `uav0000339_00001_v`.

From the original VisDrone annotations, only pedestrian-related categories were retained, including *pedestrian* and *person*. All other object categories were removed. The filtered annotations were then converted into YOLO-compatible format using normalized bounding box coordinates.

For each annotated object, the normalized bounding box parameters were computed as:

$$x_{\text{norm}} = \frac{x + \frac{w}{2}}{W}, \quad y_{\text{norm}} = \frac{y + \frac{h}{2}}{H} \quad (1)$$

$$w_{\text{norm}} = \frac{w}{W}, \quad h_{\text{norm}} = \frac{h}{H} \quad (2)$$

where x and y denote the top-left corner coordinates of the bounding box, w and h represent the width and height of the object region, and W and H correspond to the image width and height, respectively.

Frames without valid pedestrian annotations were excluded during preprocessing to ensure dataset consistency and improve training quality.

B. Image Tiling and Patch Formation

Human instances in UAV imagery typically occupy very limited pixel regions because of the high-altitude imaging perspective. To improve the representation of small-scale targets during model training, a patch-based image tiling strategy was implemented. Each aerial frame was divided into overlapping patches of size 640×640 pixels. A patch overlap of 20% was maintained to ensure that pedestrians positioned near patch boundaries were preserved across adjacent patches, thereby minimizing object truncation.

The stride between two consecutive patches was computed as:

$$\text{Stride} = \text{TileSize} \times (1 - \text{Overlap})$$

For the adopted configuration:

$$\text{Stride} = 640 \times (1 - 0.20) = 512$$

Bounding-box annotations intersecting a patch were remapped into the corresponding local patch coordinates, while annotations located completely outside the patch region were discarded. Furthermore, severely truncated objects and extremely small annotation fragments were removed to suppress noisy training samples. The tiling procedure increased the effective spatial representation of distant pedestrians within each patch, allowing the detection network to learn more discriminative features for small human targets in aerial scenes.

C. Dataset Partitioning Strategy

To maintain balanced scene representation across the dataset, a sequence-aware data splitting approach was applied. Tiles extracted from each UAV video sequence were randomly shuffled and divided into training and validation sets using an 85:15 partition ratio.

Performing the split independently for each sequence helped preserve variations in environmental conditions, pedestrian density, camera motion, and scene dynamics across both subsets. The prepared dataset was structured following the standard YOLO dataset organization format:

- images/train
- images/val
- labels/train
- labels/val

D. YOLOv8s Detection Architecture

The YOLOv8-small (YOLOv8s) variant was adopted as the pedestrian detection model due to its ability to provide a balance between computational efficiency and detection accuracy, making it well-suited for real-time UAV surveillance applications. The architecture incorporates a Cross Stage Partial (CSP) backbone for feature extraction, an SPPF module to enhance receptive field coverage, C2f blocks for efficient feature representation, and a PAN-FPN neck that fuses multi-scale features for detecting pedestrians at different object sizes [13]. The model was initialized with weights pretrained on the COCO dataset and subsequently fine-tuned on the aerial pedestrian dataset using transfer learning. Since the objective of this work was limited to pedestrian detection, the network was configured to recognize a single class. Additionally, training was performed at an input resolution of 1024×1024 pixels to improve the detection of small and distant pedestrians frequently encountered in aerial drone imagery.

Fig. 2. YOLOv8 Architecture [13]

E. Network Training Configuration

The detector was trained for 100 epochs using the AdamW optimization algorithm. To achieve smoother parameter updates during training, a cosine-based learning rate decay policy combined with an initial warm-up phase was adopted.

The starting learning rate was defined as:

$$lr_{\text{initial}} = 0.001$$

Regularization was introduced through weight decay:

$$\text{WeightDecay} = 5 \times 10^{-4}$$

Automatic Mixed Precision (AMP) training was activated to lower GPU memory usage and accelerate numerical computation during training.

The main hyperparameter configuration used in the experiments is presented in Table I.

F. Data Augmentation

To enhance the robustness of the detection model across diverse UAV-captured environments, several data augmentation techniques were incorporated into the training process. The applied augmentations included horizontal and vertical image flipping, HSV-based color adjustments, random scaling, spatial

TABLE I
TRAINING CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Epochs	100
Batch Size	16
Input Resolution	1024 × 1024
Optimizer	AdamW
Initial Learning Rate	0.001
Weight Decay	5 × 10 ⁻⁴
Warm-up Epochs	5
Learning Rate Scheduler	Cosine Decay
Single-Class Training	Enabled
Mixed Precision Training	Enabled

translation, mosaic composition, and random erasing operations. These transformations were designed to emulate realistic aerial surveillance challenges, including dynamic lighting conditions, viewpoint variability, drone-induced motion artifacts, and object occlusions. In particular, mosaic augmentation was activated during the initial phase of training to increase scene diversity and improve small-object representation. It was later disabled during the final training stages to support finer localization accuracy and stable convergence.

G. Custom ByteTrack-Based Tracking Inference

A custom multi-object tracker, conceptually inspired by ByteTrack and implemented entirely using NumPy and OpenCV, was developed for aerial pedestrian tracking. Unlike the original ByteTrack implementation, the proposed tracker incorporates a graveyard-based identity recovery mechanism and motion-consistency backtracking while remaining free of PyTorch, Ultralytics, and appearance-based Re-Identification (Re-ID) networks during inference. This design is particularly suitable for aerial surveillance, where pedestrians often occupy only a small number of pixels and appearance features contribute limited tracking benefit relative to their computational cost. The tracking process follows a two-stage association strategy. In the first stage, detections with confidence scores greater than `high_thresh` = 0.25 are matched with active tracks. Matching is performed using a weighted similarity score that combines Intersection-over-Union (IoU) and normalized centre-distance similarity:

$$S_1 = 0.4 \times \text{IoU} + 0.6 \times D_c \quad (3)$$

where D_c represents the normalized similarity between the centres of a detection and an existing track. When a match is found, the corresponding track is updated and its age counter is reset. Tracks that do not receive a match have their age incremented. Instead of being removed immediately, tracks exceeding `max_age` = 15 frames are transferred to a temporary graveyard buffer. The graveyard buffer enables recovery of identities that may be lost due to missed detections, motion blur, or brief occlusions. During the second association stage, unmatched detections are compared against recently removed tracks stored in the graveyard. A backtracking score is computed using spatial overlap, velocity similarity, and motion-direction consistency:

$$S_2 = 0.25 \times \text{IoU} + 0.50 \times V_p + 0.25 \times A_c \quad (4)$$

where V_p measures velocity proximity and A_c quantifies agreement in movement direction. If the resulting score exceeds `backtrack_thresh` = 0.30, the track is reactivated and its original identity is preserved. Graveyard entries remain available for recovery for up to `backtrack_window` = 25 frames, after which they are permanently discarded.

To improve motion modelling, each track maintains an exponentially smoothed velocity estimate (v_x, v_y) using a smoothing factor of α = 0.6. These velocity estimates are used to predict the expected position of recently lost tracks, improving the likelihood of successful identity recovery during short-term detection failures. Before tracking, each frame is resized to 640 × 640 using aspect-ratio-preserving letterboxing with a padding value of 114. The corresponding scaling factor and padding offsets are retained so that detection coordinates can be accurately mapped back to the original image resolution during post-processing. For visualization and behavioural analysis, the tracker stores the centroid history of each object throughout its lifetime. These historical positions are rendered as fading motion trails, with line thickness and opacity increasing toward the most recent location. The resulting visualization provides a clearer representation of movement trajectories while reducing the visual impact of detection noise and minor camera motion.

H. Deployment and Model Optimization

Following training, the optimized YOLOv8 detector was exported to the ONNX format to enable lightweight and platform-independent deployment. Graph simplification, static input dimensions, and FP16 weight conversion were applied during export using ONNX opset 17. The resulting model was executed using ONNX Runtime with CPU optimization enabled, reducing memory consumption and improving inference efficiency. Detection outputs were filtered using confidence thresholding and Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) before being passed to the proposed Custom ByteTrack-based tracking module described in the previous section.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed aerial pedestrian detection and tracking framework was evaluated using selected sequences from the VisDrone2019-MOT dataset. The system integrates a fine-tuned YOLOv8s detector with a lightweight IoU-based tracking algorithm optimized for CPU deployment.

The central contribution of the detection pipeline is the overlapping tile-based preprocessing strategy. As shown in Table II, applying 640 × 640 overlapping patches to high-resolution aerial frames yields an mAP_{50} gain of +0.378 and an mAP_{50-95} gain of +0.611 over the untiled baseline. The larger improvement at stricter IoU thresholds indicates that tiling benefits localization precision, not just coarse recall — tiling increases the apparent pixel footprint of pedestrians from approximately 4–8 px to 20–40 px within each patch, crossing the detection threshold for YOLOv8’s smallest anchor scale.

A total of 11,205 annotated image tiles were generated from four UAV sequences using a 20% overlap configuration.

TABLE II
EFFECT OF TILING ON DETECTION PERFORMANCE

	mAP@50	mAP@50-95	Prec.	Recall	F1
w/o tiling	0.564	0.169	0.865	0.590	0.702
w/ tiling	0.942	0.780	0.960	0.930	0.950
Gain	+0.378	+0.611	+0.095	+0.340	+0.248

The resulting detector achieves an mAP₅₀ of 0.942 and mAP₅₀₋₉₅ of 0.78, with precision 0.96, recall 0.93, and F1-score 0.95, confirming reliable detection under challenging UAV conditions including altitude variation, crowd density, occlusion, and motion blur.

For deployment, the trained YOLOv8s model was exported to ONNX format with FP16 precision. The final model size was approximately 22 MB and achieved an inference speed of nearly 6.6 FPS on CPU using ONNX Runtime, demonstrating suitability for lightweight edge-based aerial surveillance applications.

Fig. 3. Confusion Matrix

Overall, the proposed framework achieves an effective balance between detection accuracy, tracking consistency, and computational efficiency for UAV-based pedestrian monitoring systems.

V. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Although the proposed framework achieves encouraging results for aerial pedestrian detection and tracking, several limitations remain. The current study was conducted using four sequences from the VisDrone2019-MOT validation dataset. Consequently, the reported performance may not fully represent behaviour under all flight conditions, camera altitudes, weather variations, or crowd distributions. Future experiments on additional UAV benchmarks such as VisDrone2020-MOT and UAVDT would provide a broader assessment of system reliability across different operational scenarios. The proposed tracker relies on motion and overlap information for identity maintenance. While the graveyard mechanism helps recover

Fig. 4. Sample detection output, VisDrone2019-MOT val set

short-term disappearances, identities that remain absent for extended periods cannot be re-associated once their records are removed from memory. Incorporating lightweight appearance descriptors or compact visual embeddings may improve recovery after prolonged occlusions without substantially increasing computational cost. The detection stage employs fixed tile sizes and overlap settings throughout processing. An adaptive tiling strategy that automatically adjusts these parameters based on scene content, target density, or estimated flight altitude could further improve detection consistency for small, distant pedestrians. Finally, the CPU implementation currently operates at approximately 6.6 FPS, which may not satisfy the requirements of time-critical UAV applications. Future optimization efforts will focus on deployment on embedded AI hardware, including NVIDIA Jetson platforms, together with model compression, quantization, and additional ONNX Runtime acceleration techniques to improve inference throughput.

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